

ISic0613

Fragments of a painted library catalogue

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

painted text

Material

stucco

Object

painted wall

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2017.03.22

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance

The fragments were found in 1969, without clear dating evidence, in the fill of a large cistern within an ancient building containing a small peristyle courtyard - most likely a rich private house - on the slopes below the theatre (adjoining via Bagnoli Croci, next to the modern Hotel Taormina Park)

Coordinates

37.850795, 15.291562

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Antiquarium del Teatro Antico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Painted

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 3-8 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI330113

1. Καλλισθένης Ὀλύν[θιος]·
2. ἐγένετο μὲν κ[αὶ Ἄ]-
3. λεξάνδρου ἐπισ[το]-
4. λαγράφος· ἀπ' οὗ ἡ [μ]-
5. πεδεκῶς πράξε [ις]
6. διαγράφειν τῶν [— —]
7. [— — — —]ως ἐ [— — —]
8. [— — — — — — — — —]
- 9.
10. [Παραβάλλ(?)]ων Ἡλεῖος
11. [— — — — — — — — —]Σ
12. [— — — — — — — — —]ΛΓ [— —]
- 13.

15. [— — — — — — — — —]

16.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 494031

EDCS 55702035

PHI 330113

PHI 340077

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2009.0437

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2006.0515

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 61.0761

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 59.1131

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 56.1106

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 52.0936bis

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 51.1390

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 47.1464

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 26.1123

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique.* At 1976.0820

Horsfall, N. 1976. Q. Fabius C. filius Pictor; some new evidence. *Liverpool Classical Monthly.* 1: 18.

Manganaro, G. 2000. Review of Società e cultura nella Sicilia antica (1997). *Epigraphica.* 62: 311-317. At 311-312

- Battistoni, F. 2006. The ancient pinakes from Tauromenion. Some new readings.. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik*. 157: 169-180.
- Horsfall, N. 1976. Q. Fabius C. filius Pictor; some new evidence. *Liverpool Classical Monthly*. 1: 18.
- Manganaro, G. 1974. Una biblioteca storica nel ginnasio di Tauromenion e il P.Oxy. 1241. *PdP*. 29: 389-409.
- Manganaro, G. 1976. Una biblioteca storica nel ginnasio a Tauromenion nel II sec. a.C.. In Alfoeldi, A.(eds.), *Roemische Fruereschichte: Kritik und Forschung seit 1964*. Heidelberg: Carl Winter. pp. 83-96.
- Manganaro, G. 2011. La syggeneia dei Centuripini e dei Lanuvini, il lemma di Fabio Pittore a Tauromenion e il fr. 23 Morel del Bellum Poenicum di Nevio. In Deroux, C.(eds.), *Corolla Epigraphica. Hommages au professeur Yves Burnand*. Brussels. pp. 549-561.
- Blanck, H. 1997. Un nuovo frammento del 'catalogo' della biblioteca di Tauromenion. *PdP*. 52: 241-255.
- Dillery, J. 2002. Quintus Fabius Pictor and Greco-Roman historiography at Rome. In Miller, J.F., Damon, C., Myers, K.S.(eds.), *Vertis in usum. Studies in Honor of Edward Courtney*. Leipzig. pp. 1-23.
- Battistoni, F. 2009. I pinakes di Tauromenion: alcune osservazioni. In Ampolo, C. (eds.), *Immagine e immagini della Sicilia e di altre isole del Mediterraneo antico*. Pisa. pp. 811-815.

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